

Analysis of the usage of linear algebra in image processing

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Abstract

In this work, we will explore image processing and its connection to linear algebra. We will demonstrate how image manipulations are applications of powerful matrix operations. We will also investigate examples of image processing prevalent in everyday life.

Keywords: linear algebra, image processing, matrix, compression

1 Introduction

An image is made up of a discrete set of data possessing both special (position) and intensity (color/darkness/brightness) values. Image processing is a method to perform operations on a image to accomplish a certain goal or extract information from it. It is a form of signal processing, in which the input is an image and the output is another image or features present in the original. Image processing algorithms follow the following steps:

1. Importing the image
2. Analysis, manipulation, and modification of the image
3. Export of results containing an altered image or a report based on analysis

There are primarily two types of image processing methods: analog and digital processing. Analog methods are typically used for hard copies like newspapers, printouts, and photographs. There are various fundamental techniques used in this style of image processing, however, they are out of scope for this

work. Digital image processing helps in the manipulation and analysis of digital images using computer programs and algorithms.

2 Digital Image Processing

2.1 Definition

Digital image processing is the use of a digital computer to process digital images through an algorithm. It is a subcategory of digital signal processing, and has many advantages of analog image processing. It can allow for a much wider range of algorithms to be applied to the input image, and can process information at an enhanced speed and quality when compared to analog image processing.

Digital image processing passes through three general phases of processing: pre-processing, enhancement and display, and information extraction. Digital processing has two main tasks:

1. Process image data for storage and application by autonomous machine perception (transmission and representation).
2. Improvement of pictorial information in the original image.

2.2 History of digital image processing

A majority of the techniques developed in digital image processing were developed in the 1960s at Bell Laboratories, the Jet Propulsion Laboratory, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, University of Maryland, and a few other research facilities across the United States. They were developed with application to wire-photos, satellite imagery, medical imaging, videophone, photograph enhancement and character recognition.

Early image processing served to improve the quality of an image. The input was a low-quality image, and the output was an image with improved quality. The first application was by the American Jet Propulsion Laboratory, using image processing techniques on lunar photos sent back by the Space Detector Ranger 7 in 1964. They used techniques such as geometric correction, gradation transformation, noise removal, etc. to allow for the successful mapping of the moon's surface.

The cost of digital image processing was initially high, due to the high cost of computing equipment in the 1960s. However, as technology developed and cheaper computers and hardware were made available, image processing became cheaper and more applicable, eventually being used in real-time for various

television sources. As the price went even lower, digital image processing became the preferred method for image processing, due to its versatility, speed, and cost-effectiveness.

2.3 The pixel as the smallest element

In a digital image, the smallest manipulable element is the pixel. Serving as the "atom" of an image, the number and density of pixels depends on the quality of the camera used to take the picture. Modern images contain range between 24-bit and 32-bit systems. Modern displays express their quality in megapixels, where the number, in millions, of pixels displayed. Higher numbers allow for higher quality photos to be displayed.

Pixels represent colors through color blending. Colors are generated using base colors, with the most popular system being red-green-blue (RGB) and cyan-magenta-yellow-key (CMYK). The RGB system is the more common, used in most computer displays. Each base color in the RGB system contains 256 gradients, and the color is represented by the value of the red, green, and blue components. This means that there are 256^3 pixels, or 16,777,216 different colors a pixel can represent.

The three images below show the progression of detail as we zoom into a photo.

2.4 The image represented by a matrix

Using the logic from the last section, we can see that each pixel is represented by three numbers. Each color is represented by a one dimensional matrix containing three sets. Examples of the matrix values for familiar colors are given in the table below:

Color	Red (R)	Green (G)	Blue (B)
red	255	0	0
green	0	255	0
blue	0	0	255
black	0	0	0
white	255	255	255
orange	255	128	0
yellow	255	255	0
magenta	255	0	255

Thus, we can create a three-dimensional matrix that represents any image. Two dimensions will represent the location of the pixel, and the third dimension will contain three elements, representing the values of color in the RGB system.

2.5 Matrix operations on images

Since we can now represent images as three-dimensional matrices, it follows that our standard matrix operations represent image transformations. We will look at the following three common operations:

1. Multiplication by a constant
2. Addition
3. Compression

2.5.1 Multiplication by a constant

Multiplying an image by a constant simply serves to multiply each color value by that constant. If the multiplication results in a value larger than 255, it will simply stay at 255. This multiplication serves to change the constant of a image.

2.5.2 Addition

Adding two images simply adds the values for color in both images together. Similarly to multiplying, if the addition results in a value larger than 255, it will simply stay at 255. This serves to combine two images, while also changing the constant. However, it will not change the contrast in a uniform manner.

2.5.3 Compression

Compression is the interesting operation when it comes to image processing. Matrix compression can be done in a variety of ways, and the methods rely on finding patterns in the matrix. An example is removing the extra zeros in a

matrix to take less storage.

Since an image, by its nature, will contain many patterns and zeros, compression techniques can serve to greatly reduce the size of images in storage. Examples of algorithms in linear algebra include diagonalization, pruning, low-rank approximations, and quantization. A variety of methods are used by digital image processing algorithms to reduce the size of images.

3 Applications of digital image processing

Ever since the development of digital image processing, there have been many applications to the real world. Some of the biggest applications are in face detection, social media/photoshop technologies, image quality improvement algorithms, and in space exploration.

Facial recognition algorithms revolve around comparing images to their database, and then returning a result of information about the face(s). This is done by an algorithm that converts the image into a matrix, which can then be compared to a database in a variety of ways using linear algebra tools and techniques. This facial recognition can be used in phones and accounts to allow easier access to personal information normally secured with a password.

Social media and photoshop programs are also major applications of image processing. Filters and layers can be used to edit and better images before posting them for the world to see. These filters are simply matrix operations that are editing the original image's matrix through linear algebra techniques.

Image quality is an important element of images, and it is hard to control, as it can be influenced by camera vibration/motion, over-exposure, gray-level distribution, and background noise. Images can be smoothed out, removing jumps in color from errors, through convolution, and histogram equalization can change the gray scale to a more uniform pattern. These methods are used in a variety of applications, from smartphones improving image quality to governmental agencies like the National Security Agency (NSA) and the Central Intelligence Agency (CIA) to preserve national security from information in photos.

NASA also uses digital matrix processing to accomplish its mission to drive advances in science, technology, aeronautics, and space exploration to enhance knowledge, education, innovation, economic vitality, and stewardship of Earth. It does this by using advanced imagery sensors to capture details about Earth, other planets, and the cosmos, and use image processing to extract valuable information from these images. Google Maps uses satellite imagery manipulated with image processing to capture the Earth in detail and accuracy. These algorithms and operate in real and near-real time all rely on linear algebra to

analyze and manipulate the images through their matrix.

4 Conclusion

Image processing is a compilation of techniques and methods to analyze and manipulate images to either change them or extract information from them. During the early stages, costs made the technology available only to governmental agencies and large universities, but as technological developments spurred the creation of cheaper software and hardware, image processing has spread to encompass almost all aspects of our daily lives. From medical imaging to social media posts, the prevalence of image processing was made possible by the fundamental algorithms in linear algebra, and the application of them to images in matrix form.

This work has provided an overview of image processing, and demonstrated the applications of linear algebra into the process.

5 References

Below are a list of sources used to create this work.

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